

A new synthesis method of methyl jasmonate

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Abstract : Methyl jasmonate was synthesized from *cis*-4-heptenoic acid via acylation, aminolysis, grafting, deprotection, cyclization etc. in seven steps. The procedure was simple and suitable for industrialization. The product structures were characterized by ¹H NMR, MS and elemental analysis.

Keywords : Methyl jasmonate, synthesis, *cis*-4-heptenoic acid.

Introduction

Methyl jasmonate, a natural constituent of jasmine oil and Tunisia rosemary oil, has become a valuable raw material in modern perfumery. Its fragrance is full-bodied and gentle and its aroma lasts much longer than methyl dihydrojasmonate. It is indispensable in the production of jasmine fragrance. But for a few industrialized synthesis routes, the use of methyl jasmonate is limited due to its high price.

Most of the methods for preparation of methyl jasmonate described in the literature have disadvantages such as the lengthy routes and the relatively inaccessible substances^{1,2}. Here, an efficient seven steps method for preparation of methyl jasmonate in good yield from *cis*-4-heptene acid³ was developed which allowed the production of methyl jasmonate on a large scale. This process has received considerable attention as a result of

new methods of synthesizing 1,4-diketones which were key intermediates to get the cyclopentenone system. An early synthesis from Grignard reagent and acyl chloride results in low yield and required harsh reaction conditions. We have investigated the condensation reaction of *N*-methyl-*N*-methoxy-amide with Grignard reagent^{4,5} and found the yield of product **4** almost quantitative. This improvement simplified the process, increased the yield, and made this route suitable for industrialization.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents used were analytical grade material obtained from market. Silica gel GF254 is used for TLC. THF has been dealt with dehydration. All other chemicals were used without further purification. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a 400 MHz spectrometer with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard.

Scheme 1. The synthesis route for methyl jasmonate.

*Preparation :**Synthesis of compound 2 :*

128.0 g (1.0 mol) *cis*-4-heptenoic acid and 179.0 g (1.5 mol) SOCl₂ were added to a flask at 0 °C in ice bath, and then stirred at room temperature overnight. The excess SOCl₂ was separated by vacuum distillation. Crude product **2** was obtained and could be used directly for next step reaction.

Synthesis of compound 3 :

73.3 g (0.5 mol) compound **2**, 48.5 g (0.5 mol) *N,O*-dimethyl hydroxylamine hydrochloride and 200 mL trichloromethane were added to a reaction flash, 96.0 g (1.2 mol) pyridine was added dropwise consecutively at 0 °C in water bath and then stayed overnight. The mixture was washed successively with diluted hydrochloric acid and NaHCO₃ solution and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed by rotating evaporation, and vacuum distillation afforded pure compound **3**⁶ (78.4 g, 91.7%); b.p. 84~86 °C/(1 mm Hg); ¹H NMR δ : 5.38 (2H, m, CHCH), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.18 (3H, s, NCH₃), 2.36–2.46 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂), 2.06 (2H, t, CH₂CO), 0.96 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃); EI-MS (*m/z*) : 171 [M⁺]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for C₉H₁₇NO₂ : C, 63.13; H, 10.01; N, 8.18; Found : C, 63.08; H, 9.97; N, 8.25.

Synthesis of compound 4 :

14.4 g (0.6 mol) Mg, a grain of I₂ and 100 mL anhydrous THF were mixed in a reaction flash, then 1 g 2-(2-bromoethyl)-1,3-dioxolane⁷ was added under N₂ atmosphere. The mixture was heated to initiate the reaction until the color of I₂ faded. Afterwards the solution of 90.5 g (0.5 mol) 2-(2-bromoethyl)-1,3-dioxolane in 100 mL THF was added dropwise under tender boiling and the solution maintain reflux for 1 h after addition. When the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, the solution of 68.4 g (0.4 mol) compound **3** in 100 mL THF was added at 0 °C in ice bath and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The solution was then neutralized with HCl aqueous solution and extracted with ethyl acetate, and the organic extracts were washed with NaCl solution, and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed by rotating evaporation, and vacuum distillation afforded pure compound **4**⁸ (77.1 g, 90.9%); b.p. 101~104 °C/(1 mm Hg);

¹H NMR δ : 5.28–5.37 (2H, m, CHCH), 4.91 (1H, t, *J* 5 Hz, CH), 3.84–3.94 (4H, m, OCH₂CH₂O), 2.46–2.52 (4H, m, CH₂COCH₂), 1.96–2.30 (6H, m, CH₂), 0.96 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃); EI-MS (*m/z*) : 212 [M⁺]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for C₁₂H₂₀O₃ : C, 67.89; H, 9.50; Found : C, 68.02; H, 9.58.

Synthesis of compound 5⁹ :

63.6 g (0.3 mol) compound **4**, 30 mL 4 *N* HCl and 100 mL THF were added into the reaction flash and heated for 3 h at 50 °C. The organic phase was extracted with ethyl acetate and washed successively with 10% NaHCO₃ solution, NaCl solution and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed by rotating evaporation and vacuum distillation afforded pure compound **5** (41.5 g, 82.3%, yield); b.p. 110~115°/(1.5 mm Hg); ¹H NMR δ : 9.80 (1H, s, CHO), 5.28–5.39 (2H, m, CHCH), 2.74–2.75 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂), 2.53 (2H, t, CH₂), 2.29–2.38 (2H, t, CH₂), 2.04–2.08 (2H, m, CH₂), 0.96 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃); EI-MS (*m/z*) : 168 [M⁺]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for C₁₀H₁₆O₂ : C, 71.39, H, 9.59; Found : C, 71.46; H, 9.54.

Synthesis of compound 6¹⁰ :

33.6 g (0.2 mol) compound **5**, 20 mL NaOH (1%) solution and 60 mL THF were added to reaction mixture and heated for 4 h at 40 °C. The organic phase was extracted with ethyl acetate and washed with saturated NaCl solution to neutral, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Then vacuum distillation afforded pure compound **6** (22.6 g, 75.3% yield); b.p. 100~105°/(1.0 mm Hg); ¹H NMR δ : 7.30 (1H, m, COCCH), 5.43–5.51 (2H, m, CHCH), 2.89–2.92 (2H, t, CH₂), 2.55–2.57 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.40–2.43 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.06 (2H, m, CH₂), 0.97 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃); EI-MS (*m/z*) : 150 [M⁺]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for C₁₀H₁₄O : C, 79.96; H, 9.39; Found : C, 79.93; H, 9.31.

Synthesis of compound 7¹¹ :

The solution of 15.0 g (0.1 mol) compound **6** in 30 mL methanol was dropwise added into the mixture of 60 mL methanol, 0.23 g Na (0.01 mol) and 13.2 g (0.1 mol) dimethyl malonate at 0 °C in water bath. After 1 h, 1 g acetic acid and 70 mL water were added into the reaction mixture. The mixture was extracted with Et₂O (30 mL × 3). The combined organic extracts were washed with water

and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The crude product **7** (26.4 g, 93.6% yield) was obtained at 140~143 °C/(0.1 mm Hg) by vacuum distillation; $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$: 5.38–5.49 (2H, m, CHCH), 3.70 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 3.47 (1H, s, CH(COOMe) $_2$), 1.75–2.50 (10H, m, CH_2), 0.95 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3); EI-MS (m/z) : 282 [M^+]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$: C, 63.81; H, 7.85; Found : C, 63.73; H, 7.79.

Synthesis of compound **8** :

16.92 g (0.06 mol) compound **7** was added dropwise consecutively into 50 mL NaOH (10%) solution. The mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight and then was added dilute sulphuric acid. After the reaction mixture was placed under reflux for 5 h in oil bath, the heterogeneous mixture was then cooled to room temperature and extracted with Et_2O (30 mL \times 3). The combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in 60 mL methanol with catalytic amount of concentrated sulfuric acid. After the mixture reacted at 60 °C for 3 h, the methanol was removed by rotating evaporation and vacuum distillation afforded compound **8**¹² (8.87 g, 65.9% yield); b.p. 135~136 °C/(1 mm Hg); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$: 5.24–5.46 (2H, m, CHCH), 3.70 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.52–2.73 (12H, m), 0.96 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3); EI-MS (m/z) : 224 [M^+]. Elemental analysis Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 69.61; H, 8.99; Found : C, 69.52; H, 8.93.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have developed an efficient and simple method for producing methyl jasmonate. The reaction conditions are mild and the products are easily separated by simple method. High yield allows the production of methyl jasmonate on a large scale.

References

1. K. Oshima, H. Yamamoto and H. Nozaki, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 4446.
2. A. Meyers and N. Nazarenko, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1973, **38**, 175.
3. S. Kano, T. Yokomatsu, H. Iwasawa and S. Shibuya, *Heterocycles*, 1987, **26**, 359.
4. Y. Sasaki, D. Kato and D. Boger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 13533.
5. G. Wang, Y. Zou, Z. Li and Q. Wang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 5825.
6. R. Nilsson and B. Wickberg, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 2783.
7. G. Büchi and H. Wüest, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 1122.
8. M. Mikolajczyk and W. Midura, *Nouveau Journal de Chimie*, 1986, **10**, 567.
9. S. Kanemasa, T. Otsuka and K. Doi, *Synthesis*, 1990, 1167.
10. G. Stork, A. Ozorio and A. Leong, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, **19**, 5175.
11. G. Büchi and B. Egger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1971, **36**, 2021.
12. K. Hideaki, Y. Toshiro, G. Kuniaki and T. Jiro, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 4107.

